

FORMATION OF TEXT-FORMATING COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE
PROCESS OF LITERARY EDUCATION BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

Raykhan Rasulova

Department of Uzbek Literary Studies, Chirchik State Pedagogical University, p.p.f.d. (PhD)

Abstract. This article examines the formation of text-creative competence in students based on an integrative approach in the process of literary education.

Keywords. Literary education, competence, innovative technologies, text creation, integration, comparison, quality of education, novel, drama, training, analysis

Currently, a new, competency-oriented educational paradigm is developing, which represents a change in emphasis in education, involving preparation for the implementation of a personality-oriented approach of an individual who is independent, creative thinking, and able to work in a team. will help in the educational process. The development of a competency-based approach in education cannot be achieved without the development of technologies that ensure the achievement of qualitatively new practical goals in human life. One of the main reforms is the tasks provided for by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 30, 2019 No. PQ-4433 “On measures to improve the system of attracting youth to the field of science and supporting their initiatives.” solve these problems positively. Finding a way to the hearts of modern youth with the help of literature, to understand the world of literature is one of the urgent tasks. Because in modern society, Internet networks surround our youth in all aspects related to reading books. In such a precarious situation, literature teachers are in great demand for cognitive abilities, creativity, high dedication to the profession and keeping up with the times. A fact that does not require proof is that the main task in organizing the educational process is the effective use of educational technologies. But until now, most educational technology has been devoted to theoretical problems, and its influence on practice has been less noticeable. To do this, it is necessary to develop methods for more rapid implementation of modern technologies. Educational integration is a high level of interdisciplinary communication, a tool that allows you to create a whole integrated knowledge. The definitions given to the concept of integration are different, the common aspect of these definitions is that integration is about achieving a holistic view of the existence around us. In short, raising students to the level of real readers can only be done when literary education reflects the integrity of the relationship with the environment and existence.

It is advisable to implement an integrative approach in each lesson, from each small text to the analysis of a work of art. An integrative approach increases the effectiveness of the meaning of existence, so that every reader can understand the essence of the work, feel the emotions of the characters, live the life created in the work, and most importantly, draw conclusions from the events in the work. work or think critically about them.

For example, the content and essence of the epic “Gyorogly”, given in the textbook “Literature” of the 11th grade, seems somewhat unnatural to the younger generation, especially our young teachers, which, in turn, may bore students. It is difficult to explain the events that reveal the main content of the epic without separating the text from the work, and as a result of unusual events, students may develop mistrust and misunderstanding of literature. In this situation, an integrative approach to the analysis of works of art in literature lessons is appropriate. It is difficult

to convince today's youth of events such as the birth of a living child from a mother lying in the grave and the milk coming from her breast to feed the child. In such a situation, a high level of professional competence is required from the teacher, otherwise we can cause in our younger generation such vices as distrust and disrespect for literature, as well as for the beliefs of our ancestors. We know that Gorogly's mother was a very honest and pure woman, she stubbornly endured all the suffering for her chastity, and for this, by the miracle of God and the grace of God, her child was born and lived to adulthood. It is necessary to prepare students for the lesson by giving examples from hadiths and the lives of great saints. For example, in Khuwaido's "Rohati Dil", one can tell the story of a princess who was buried alive and brought safely out of the grave by a brave young man, who supposedly died due to a serious illness. During the extraction process, the young man grabbed the princess by the hand and pulled her out of the tomb. As a result of this honest and well-intentioned marriage, Ibrahim Adham, the world-famous saint of Sufism, was born. Now let's talk about why we compared it with "Rohati Dil". The main content of the work "Rohati Dil" is explained in the title of the work. In this work, people who have lived purely and honestly are rewarded by the excellence of their children, and it is proven that the tongue of any parent will be rewarded. enjoy it. As can be seen from the above examples, it is not an exaggeration to say that the main content of the two works is to live purely and honestly, and also to reveal the difficult and sad consequences of disloyalty and ignorance.

In addition, we can also integrate fantasy works in relation to epic. We can also use today's discoveries of the fantastic imagination dreamed up by our ancestors.

Based on these examples, an integrative approach should be effectively used to explain the essence of the two works.

Using this approach, we develop students' comparison and contrast skills. This will teach them to independently express their opinions and defend them. This helps us make lessons interesting and increase the effectiveness of the lesson.

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In conclusion, special attention should be paid to the issue of studying literature, which is important for students' education. After all, intellectually mature students are creators of the future.

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